

GENDER RESPONSIVE MODULE AND CLOTHING CONSTRUCTION COMPETENCIES OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS IN TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on development of the Gender-responsive Module in Technology and Livelihood Education for Clothing Construction for Grade 10 which composed of five competencies aiming to determine the perception of the student-respondents regarding the acceptability and extent of consideration in five gender principles of the said learning material, lastly, identify the competency level performance of student-respondents after the use of this gender-responsive module. This is a descriptive-developmental type of research intending to produce gender responsive approach learning module. Majority of the respondents were 16 -20 years old female having 57.30% of the eighty two (82) total population. Findings regarding the overall perception of the student respondents in the gender-responsive module shows overall mean of 3.06, they find the learning module acceptable. While the overall result mean of 3.31 indicating consideration to gender principles is perceived by the respondents as highly extent. Pre-test and Post-test of the respondents in all the Clothing Construction Competencies, with the overall result of t-value 15.474 with the no significant difference result of .0000, shows that with the 95% level of confidence and a p value of .05, reveals that the very minimal increase of the posttest from the pre-test is the reason why there is no significant difference. Significant relationship of Gender Principles in terms of Sensitivity to the five Clothing Construction Competencies, the finding shows that there is no significant relationship in terms of taking body measurements with r-value = -.110, drafting pattern is -.109, finishing is -.059. Only laying out pattern and cutting fabrics has significant relationship with r-value = .252*. Gender principle "Discrimination" has no significant relationship to the Clothing Construction Competencies in terms of taking body measurement with r-value = -.059, for drafting pattern is r-value-.072,, for assembling r-value =.099 and for finishing r-value = -.114.Only laying out and cutting and the fabric has significant relationship having r-value for is .266*. Gender principle Sensitivity and discrimination on the other hand resulted to have significant relationship with the gender-responsive module competency "Cutting and laying out the fabric".

Keywords: Gender Responsive Module, Clothing Construction Competency, Gender Principles